

Quantitative determination of vanadium in Bayer's liquor and vanadium sludge using ICP-AES

Upendra Singh* and S. P. Puttewar

Analytical Research Division, Jawaharlal Nehru Aluminium Research Development & Design Centre,
Amravati Road, Wadi, Nagpur-440 023, Maharashtra, India

E-mail : singhu1970@rediffmail.com Fax : 91-7104-220942

Abstract : Quantification of vanadium (as V_2O_5) in Bayer liquor (Spent) and precipitated vanadium sludge have been done using ICP-AES and classical methods. Samples were prepared by acid digestion technique for the complete dissolution of free as well as bound vanadium in highly alkaline samples. Concentration of vanadium in spent liquor was obtained to be 1.2 gpl to 2.8 gpl and 11.2 to 17.8% as V_2O_5 in the sludge collected from different Indian alumina refineries.

In this paper, optimization of operating condition of ICP-AES, sample preparation methodology, validation of data and their significance has been studied. Precision of measurement in the standards sample and industrial samples were indicated by % RSD which was achieved as low as 0.9. A comparative study of conventional (classical) and instrumental (ICP-AES) methods in the determination of vanadium for liquor and sludge have been discussed.

Keywords : ICP-AES, Bayer's liquor, AND, vanadium sludge.

Introduction

During processing of Bauxite for the production of alumina, bauxite is digested in a solution of caustic soda in autoclaves. Impurities like iron oxide, silicon oxide and titanium oxide are removed by allowing the solution to settle and filtration. After removal of the impurities the resultant solution contains hydrate alumina, caustic soda and small quantities of other chemical impurities of metal including vanadium in the dissolved state. Alumina hydrate is precipitated from the solution and the remaining solution is known as (Bayer liquor) spent liquor.

The spent liquor contains caustic soda, small quantities of other chemical compounds of metals including vanadium. The caustic soda in the spent liquor can be recycled and re-used for digesting further quantity of bauxite and production of alumina. The spent liquor is subjected to the process of concentration for the removal of vanadium. The concentrated liquor is taken to a chilled tank where temperature is brought down to around 20 °C. At this temperature, vanadium salt gets crystallized out of the liquor. This vanadium salt contains vanadium compound predominantly in the form of sodium orthovanadate ($Na_3VO_4 \cdot 12H_2O$)^{1,2}.

Analytical chemists use the different physical and chemical methods to determine the content and concentration of the atomic and molecular species present in a chemical system. Inductively coupled plasma spectroscopy (ICP-AES) is an emission spectrophotometric technique; the excited electrons emit energy at a particular wavelength as they return to ground state. The fundamental characteristic of this process is that each element emits energy at specific wavelengths typical to its chemical properties. Although each element emits energy at multiple wavelengths in ICP-AES technique but selecting a single wavelength is most common for a given element. The intensity of the energy emitted at the selected wavelength is proportional to the amount (concentration) of that element in the analytes solution. By determining the wavelength which is emitted by a sample analytes and by measuring their intensities, it can quantify the elemental composition of the given sample relative to a certified reference standard. During ICP-AES determination the sample is subjected to temperatures as high as 8000–10,000 K, where even the most refractory elements are atomized with high efficiency. As a result, detection limits for these elements can be orders of magnitude lower than other

techniques, typically at the 1–10 parts-per-billion level^{3,4}. In this technique, analysis requires a sample to be in solution. Ore/mineral samples, Bayer liquor and sludge must be dissolved in mineral acids. This can be achieved by acid digestion using HF, H₂SO₄, HNO₃, and HCl acids^{5,6}.

In the present communication, ICP-AES methodology for quantification, sample preparation, optimization of procedure, selection and wavelength and mapping compared to classical method of analysis for vanadium in liquor and sludge have been studied and discussed.

Materials and methods :

Equipments :

Elemental determination was conducted by inductively coupled plasma spectrometer (ICP-AES Model Iris-Intrepid-II XDL), Thermo Electron Corporation, USA. The double distilled water was used during all the dilutions purpose was prepared by quartz distillation unit.

Reagents and chemicals :

Sulphuric acid-nitric acid mixture : Mix two volumes of dilute sulphuric acid (1 : 3) with one volume of diluted HNO₃ (1 : 1), standard KMnO₄ solution (0.2 N), ferrous ammonium sulphate solution (0.1 N), potassium ferricyanide solution : 0.1 % (w/v), ammonium persulphate : 15% (w/v) in distilled water.

Elemental standard, vanadium (1000 ppm) of high purity (99.99 was procured from Thermo Electron Corporation, UK and Qualigens India Ltd.). Working standards were prepared by dilution used for calibration, method development and optimization of methods. Both liquor and sludge were collected from Indian Aluminium Industries. All the dilutions were done using double distilled/de-ionized water.

Methods of sample preparation :

Bayer's liquor :

Pipette out 10 ml sample liquor and filtered into 100 ml volumetric flask, shake well and make up to the mark. Taken 5 ml of diluted sample into a 100 ml beaker and

warmed gently for few min, added 5 ml conc. nitric acid-hydrochloric acid mixture (1 : 2) and transferred the whole solution into 50 ml volumetric flask. Cooled the mixture and make up to the mark and use for analysis, similarly reagent blank was also prepared with acid and distilled water.

Vanadium sludge :

2.0 g of vanadium sludge sample was taken in a 600 ml beaker and added 80 ml sulphuric acid-nitric acid mixture (as prepared). Heat on the hot plate till dense white fumes of sulphur dioxide appears. Cooled and added distilled water and heated until salt was dissolved.

Results and discussion

Quantitative analysis (Classical methods) :

Quantification by vanadium sludge by titration method :

Dilute the prepared sample to 400 ml, cool to room temperature and add standard 0.2 N KMnO₄ solution until a strong pink color has developed which persists for at least 30 s. Cool the solution to 15 °C and reduce vanadium by adding ferrous ammonium sulphate solution till the presence of Fe²⁺ is indicated by the ferricyanide spot test (out side test on white ceramic plate). Add 5 ml of ferrous ammonium sulphate solution in excess with constant stirring the solution for a minute. Cool to 15 °C and oxidize the excess of Fe²⁺ with 8 to 10 ml of ammonium persulphate solution. Stir the solution vigorously for few minute. Titrate the solution with standard KMnO₄ solution until a faint pink color appears and persists for more than 20–30 s. End point of the titration was very difficult to notice as it disappears very fast. Total time of analysis requires 4–5 h. Analysis of two sludge sample of different Indian refineries have been carried out and reported in Table 1.

$$\text{Calculations : \% } V_2O_5 = \frac{V \times N \times \text{Factor}}{W}$$

V = Volume in ml of standard KMnO₄ solution used for titration, N = Normality of the standard KMnO₄ solution and W = Weight of the sample taken in g.

Table 1. Calibration report of vanadium using 10 ppm standard solution

Element	Line	Unit	Obtained values			Average	SD	% RSD
			10.46	10.16	10.28			
V	311.071	Cts/s	10.46	10.16	10.28	10.3	0.154	0.255

Quantification of vanadium in spent liquor by colorimetric method :

Pipette out 5 ml aliquot of the diluted sample; add 7.0 ml of 70% HClO₄ carefully. Take 50 ml distilled water into a 100 ml volumetric flask for blank. Add 7.0 ml HClO₄ to the flask. Evaporate the solution in the beaker to near dryness. Dissolve the salts in little hot water as possible. Add distilled water to the beaker to make the volume up to 30 ml. Filter the solution and total volume in 100 ml flask must not exceed 50 ml. Pipette 10 ml of 1 : 1 nitric acid into both flasks and mix. Pipette out 5 ml of 3 : 2 phosphoric acid into both flasks and mix. Pipette 5 ml of 6.6% sodium tungstate into both flasks and mix well. Boil both the flasks for 1 min on the hot plate. Digest the flasks in the hot water bath for 30 min. Cool the flasks to room temperature and make up the volume to mark with distilled water and mix well, a light yellow solution obtained and determine the absorbance of the sample at wave length 410 nm. Total time of analysis takes approx 4-5 h.

Instrumental method :

Quantitative analysis by ICP-AES :

Standard operating condition of the ICP-AES was achieved by carrying out number of repeat analysis using single wavelength. Two of each spent liquor and vanadium sludge was taken for quantification by wet chemical and ICP-AES determination for vanadium. Analysis data obtained by both the methods are presented in the Table 2.

Optimized operating conditions (ICP-AES) :

The optimized parameters of equipment (ICP-AES) achieved for spent liquor and vanadium sludge after number of trial experiments are as below.

Power	1050	W
Plasma gas flow	13.0	L/min
Auxiliary gas flow	0.75	L/min
Nebulizer concentric	Glass-high flow	
Nebulizer gas flow	0.50	L/min
Pump speed	20	rpm
Sample delay	25	s
Rinse time	22	s
Sample replicate time	14	s
Stabilization time	5	s
Replicates	3	Nos

Analytical wavelengths selection :

Wavelength selection is somewhat of an individual choice that commonly varies from analyst to analyst. However, there is a developing consensus regarding the wavelength best suited for a particular target analytes considering sample matrix. All the wavelength of vanadium, 309.311, 292.402, 310.230 and 311.071 nm were tried for calibration and intensity was recorded for them to understand the suitability of particular wavelength. The intensity (counts) was found to be maximum for the spectral line 311.071 nm both in liquor and sludge matrix. Due to highly alkaline nature of the samples other lines may not found suitable for calibration. The wavelengths selected have yielded good results in a number of determinations for both the samples.

Standardization and calibration :

ICP-AES is a comparative analytical technique, in that the instrument response (measured in "counts" units) has been calibrated against standards (vanadium, 10 ppm) in

Table 2. Comparative analytical data for vanadium (as V₂O₅) furnished by classical and instrumental methods (ICP-AES)

Sample	Analytical method	Unit	Obtained value	Std deviation	% RSD	
Bayer's process liquor	Spent liquor-1	Conventional	gpl	1.25	ND	ND
		ICP-AES*	gpl	1.18	0.134	0.52
	Spent liquor-2	Conventional	gpl	2.70	ND	ND
		ICP-AES*	gpl	2.78	0.168	0.65
Vanadium sludge	Vanadium sludge-1	Conventional	%	11.2	ND	ND
		ICP-AES*	%	11.9	0.015	0.45
	Vanadium sludge-2	Conventional	%	17.0	ND	ND
		ICP-AES*	%	17.8	0.021	0.78

*Three measurements were carried out for each sample.

Fig. 1. Standardization fit plot for vanadium using single and multiple standard solutions.

which the concentration of the element is known. The intensity of programmed lines (311.071 nm) of standard solution was determined by the instrument and a simple first order linear regression fit was used to relate the intensity to the concentration of element. R^2 value obtained to be 1 is indicative of how data is fit for the linear

curve. The calibration plot is presented in the Fig. 1.

The operating conditions of the ICP during the calibration set identical to analysis conditions, so all manipulation of gas flows, pump speeds, could not interfere the determination. Before start of the analysis 10 ppm vanadium std (E. Merck, India) solution match with matrix of

analyte sample has been taken for calibration at selected wavelength. Calibration report of standard samples are given in Table 1.

Quantitative analysis :

Run starts as soon as the calibration is completed (usually within 5 min). This is of vital importance because the first item in the sample file is a drift solution, which will be used as the master drift to correct the entire run.

During analysis, Inter-elemental effect particularly Ti, Mn and Be was also noticed in case of Bayer liquor but found to be insignificant. Total time taken for single measurement for Bayer liquor and vanadium sludge was less than 30 min. The data obtained from both classical and ICP-AES methods are presented in the Table 2 with statistical data.

Conclusion

- (i) The Inductively coupled plasma spectrometer (ICP-AES) has been employed for rapid, accurate and precise quantification of vanadium for liquor and sludge sample. Total time per sample by ICP-AES 30 min compared 4–5 h by wet chemical methods.
- (ii) Inductively coupled plasma spectrometer (ICP-AES) used in quantification for vanadium in Bayer liquor and vanadium sludge for the samples collected from Indian Refineries of alumina process sample.
- (iii) Both classical and instrumental have been utilized

for the determination of vanadium and Instrumental (ICP-AES) was found to be more precise as compared to wet chemical method.

- (iv) Classical method required more time for sample preparation (3–4 h) and titrimetry especially vanadium sludge does not give sharp end point.
- (v) Statistical data such as SD and RSD ($< 1\%$) indicates the precision of the measurements.

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Abbreviations : ND - Not detected, WCL - Wet chemical, ICP - Inductively coupled plasma, ND - Not determined, SD - Standard deviation, RSD - Relative standard deviation and GP - Gram per liter.

References

1. R. J. Pradhan, S. N. Das and S. N. Thakur, *J. Scientific and Industrial Research*, 1999, **948**, 58.
2. N. K. Kshatriya and P. K. Raghavan, 'International Conference of Non-ferrous Metal', 2005, **1**, 15.
3. Gary D. Christian, "Analytical Chemistry", 6th ed., Wiley, Singapore, 2003.
4. Upendra Singh and R. S. Mishra, *Analytical Chemistry an Indian Journal*, 2012, **1**, 11.
5. Thomas J. Manning and William R. Grow, "Inductively coupled plasma-atomic emission spectrometry", Springer-Verlang, New York, 1997.
6. M. Pinta, "Modern methods for trace element analysis", Ann Arbor Science, Michigan, 2003.

